

THE PLACE OF COMMUNITY LIBRARY IN REVOLUTIONIZING RURAL AND URBAN REALITIES FOR DEVELOPMENT AND SUSTENANCE OF A NEW NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

In the pursuit of a progressive and equitable Nigeria, the role of information access and knowledge dissemination cannot be overstated. Community libraries, as grassroots institutions occupy a critical position in bridging the developmental gap in rural and urban communities. This paper explores the transformative potential of community libraries in revolutionizing socio-economic realities and fostering national development. This paper presented community libraries in Nigeria as provider of inclusive access to educational resources, digital literacy, civic knowledge, and lifelong skills, which empower individuals across age, gender, and socio-economic lines. Community library as revealed in this paper serve not only as learning centers, but also as hubs for innovation, youth engagement, cultural preservation and democratic participation. The paper also maintained that community libraries in Nigeria face significant challenges such as poor funding, inadequate infrastructure, limited professional staffing, and low public awareness which are their constraints. The paper recommended renewed investment, policy integration and community involvement to reposition them as catalysts for the development and sustenance of a new Nigeria, which is informed, inclusive and future ready.

Key words: Community library, transformation, development, sustenance and new Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

In the pursuit of a progressive and self-sustaining Nigeria, the role of accessible knowledge and inclusive education cannot be overstated. As the nation grapples with persistent developmental disparities between rural and urban areas, community libraries emerge as powerful tools for transformation. Far beyond mere repositories of books, these libraries represent democratic spaces for learning, empowerment, innovation and civic engagement. In both rural enclaves where educational infrastructure is often lacking and in urban centers grappling with social inequalities and digital divides, the community library holds the potential to bridge gaps, nurture human capital and catalyze grassroots development (Bassey, Uzoh and Bassey, 2020).

In the context of Nigeria's complex socio-economic challenges, reimagining the community library as a center for development offers a unique pathway toward national renewal. Whether it is in promoting literacy, supporting skills acquisition, fostering entrepreneurship, or serving as hubs for youth engagement and digital inclusion, community libraries have the capacity to revolutionize realities on both ends of the rural-urban spectrum (Bassey, Uzoh and Bassey, 2020). This paper explores the transformative place of the community library in driving sustainable development and shaping the vision of a new Nigeria—one anchored on knowledge, equity and inclusive growth.

Statement of the problem

Despite Nigeria's immense human and natural resources, the nation continues to struggle with underdevelopment, high youth unemployment, poor literacy level and widening inequalities between rural and urban populations. These challenges are exacerbated by a lack of access to quality information, lifelong learning opportunities and community-based development platforms—gaps that community libraries are uniquely positioned to address.

In rural areas, educational infrastructure is often either inadequate or non-existing. Many communities suffer from limited access to books, digital resources, and safe learning space, which in turn hampers literacy, skill development, and informed civic participation (Okiy, 2010). Without access to reliable knowledge hubs, rural dwellers are often excluded from participating fully in the social, economic and political life of the nation.

Urban areas, although better resourced, are not exempted from challenges. Rising youth populations, increasing unemployment, and growing socio-economic disparities demand inclusive and innovative public spaces that foster lifelong learning, skills acquisition, and civil engagement. Unfortunately, public libraries and community learning centers in Nigerian cities are grossly inadequate, underfunded, poorly maintained, and largely ignored in development planning (Issa, Amusan & Daura, 2009). The absence of functional libraries in both rural and urban communities reflects a systemic neglect of knowledge infrastructures in national development strategies.

Moreover, Nigeria's National Policy on Education emphasizes the importance of lifelong learning and access to information for national development, yet implementation has been weak, with little investment in community library system (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2024). This disconnect has contributed to the growing digital divide, information poverty and intellectual disenfranchisement among marginalized population.

Consequently, there is an urgent need to reposition community libraries as central agents in the quest for equitable development and national renewal. When properly equipped and integrated into local development frameworks, community libraries can become catalysts for literacy, entrepreneurship, digital inclusion, and civic empowerment, which are all essential components for building a new Nigeria.

Methodology

Exploratory research design was used in this study in gaining understanding of the evolving role of community libraries in shaping both rural and urban development in Nigeria. Given the limited time and lack of prior-research in this specific area, particularly within the Nigerian context, the exploratory approach allows for an open-ended inquiry, to discover new insights and a flexibly used of secondary materials to determine how community libraries contribute to social transformation and sustainable development.

The purpose was to explore the existing state and functions of community libraries in various Nigerian settings, and also the challenges and opportunities they face in contributing to development and societal renewal. Ethically references were provided for all information used from secondary services.

Conceptual Clarification and Definitions

Community library

A community library is a dynamic, people-centered learning hub designed to meet the educational, informational, cultural, and developmental needs of a specific community. Community libraries serves as essential public spaces where individuals- regardless of socio-economic status, literacy level or location can engage in lifelong learning, personal development and civic participations. In strict conception, a community library is a library service and associated space owned by local community and is controlled by representatives of the community in a way which is responsive to the wishes and needs of the community and people therein (Bassey, Uzoh and Bassey, 2020). Community library is a type of public library which serve cities and towns of all types. A public library is the local gateway to knowledge which provides basic condition for lifelong, independent decision making in cultural development, and social groups, which must be established under the clear mandate of the law, funded by public tax in which users are not supposed to pay fees, operated by librarians, library paraprofessionals and support staff (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, 1994).

Edwards, Rauseo and Unger (2013) identifies functions or purposes of community library to include; community building; management of diversity; serving as center for arts, culture, heritage preservation and archives; promotion of learning, socialization and awareness creation; promotion of democratic values; catalyst for addressing individuals and social problems; manager of youths and provision of social business resources. Considering the functions of community library in terms of information provision, education and cultural preservation, the library is an essential agent for the fostering of peace and spiritual welfare essential for the emergence of a new Nigeria.

Community

Specifically, community refers to people who share common interest, values, goals or geographical location and who interact with one another in a meaningful and sustained way (Ottong, 2011). Key elements of community are; people, connection, commonality, support or cooperation and identify (Ottong, 2011). In the definition community is made up of individuals. Connection refers to forms of relationship or interaction among members. Commonality has to do with what members share in common, for example, location, culture, interest, belief etc. Support or cooperating refers to what communities provide for members, for example, emotional, social or material. Identity is the sense of belongingness members enjoy.

There are two major types of communities, namely; urban and rural communities (Ottong, 2011). Urban community refers to a densely populated area such as a town or city, characterized by advanced infrastructure, industrial and service-based economies and a diverse population. Example of urban centers in Nigeria are the state capitals and big towns like Lagos, Calabar, Port-Harcourt, Kano, Kaduna, Abuja etc. Rural community is typically a small, close-knit population living in the countryside, where lifestyles are centered around agriculture, natural resources, traditional values, with absent of modern infrastructure. Population density of rural areas are low, population size is small, limited infrastructure and access to services, close relationship with nature and land. Examples of rural areas in Nigeria include farming villages, remote hamlets, pastoral communities in the North and fishing settlements in the south.

New Nigeria

The idea of a new Nigeria refers to a vision or movement towards building a better, more just, prosperous, and unified Nigeria. A country transformed from its current challenges into one that truly serves the needs and aspirations of its people. According to Muddi (2023) a new Nigeria “is any aspirational concept that envisions a transformed nation founded on the principles of good governance, equity, accountability, justice, economic development, national unity and social progress. A new Nigeria represents hope, change and renewal in leadership, infrastructure, education, youth empowerment and national identity.

Philosophically, new Nigeria is based on rejecting of corruption, tribalism, nepotism and underdevelopment. It is a call for a mindset shift among both leaders and citizens. It is a firm belief in the potential of Nigerian people, especially the youth and a push for constitutional reforms aim at restructuring and decentralization of power. Achieving a new Nigeria is founded upon; leadership reform, education reform, ensuring the rule of law, sincere fight against corruption, civic engagement and inclusive development that is vital in rural and urban areas alike.

Major or core elements of a new Nigeria as presented by Uzindu (2021) are in governance, justice system, economy, education, national unity, youth empowerment, innovation, technology, security and sustainability. Government involves putting in place a transparent, accountable, people-center leadership. Justice system should ensure equal access and existence of the rule of law. Economy should be diversified to ensure growth, job creation and innovation. Quality education should be put in place to ensure creative thinking. National unity should be put in place through harmonies co-existence of diverse ethnic nationalities. Platforms should be created to foster youth engagement in decision making and leadership. Investment should be made to ensure industrial takeoff and sustenance. Peace and stability should be matters of

priority to ensure security in terms of protection of lives and properties, which entails safe environment for sustainable growth and development.

Theoretical framework

The empowerment theory of Rappaport (1981) and Zimmerman (1995) focuses on how individuals and communities gain control over their lives through access to resources, knowledge, and decision-making tools. A community library is a knowledge empowerment space, which gives people tools to solve local problems, build capacity and advocate for change. In rural areas, farmers, women and children are empowered through the library with knowledge on agriculture, health, politics, education etc. In urban areas the community library helps in supporting youth's innovation, entrepreneurship and digital literacy, thereby aligning them with global development trends. The empowerment of community people in both rural and urban areas prepares them to contribute to and participate in building and sustaining a new Nigeria.

Literature Review

Public library functions and social development

Bassey, Uzoh and Bassey (2020) identified the goal of public library as ensuring education of the public, increase awareness and increase general literacy level. They also maintain that public library which is community centered helps in personality development, human adjustment, spread of education, economic information dissemination for development, sustenance of culture and leisure. Bassey, Uzoh and Bassey (2020) concludes that library functions correlates social development objectives in terms of; promotion of culture and intergroup cohesion, information dissemination and civic activism, spread of education and awareness socialization, as well as human adjustment development and gender equality. Their study was empirical and qualitative using focus group discussion. The study was generally on social development but did not specifically deal with development aim at building a new Nigeria, though the study area was Nigeria.

Transformation of Rural Communities

Mukhtar and Kasim (2025) highlights multiple roles of community library in transforming communities in Nigeria, which includes; educational support, political awareness, economic value boost, cultural development and health awareness. They noted that when libraries are available in communities, these noble benefits will be available and enjoyed by people in the rural community. They noted the gross inadequacy of public libraries in rural communities in Nigeria, a reason which prevented the realization of the desired benefits.

Anizor, Ibeh and Alumora (2021) focuses on how libraries in Anambra State help in communal issues, showing that libraries are not just passive repositories but are seen by communities as part of local development. They maintained that public library is a veritable tool for connecting communal issues to national development which help integration of rural communities into the national development objective. This dimension is foundational for revolutionizing realities in rural areas.

Urban Libraries and Development

Adigun (2015) writing on the role of the library in bridging digital divide and transformation of society in Nigeria address how urban and rural libraries can help in building an information society, especially via information and communication, technology, but noted that urban settings still suffer from electricity problems, and insufficient broadband. In another study by Fairbairn and Lipeikaite (2014) it was presented that library in urban communities contributes to managing unemployment, skill development, awareness and contribution to public decision making, health consciousness and awareness. None of the scholars specifically examines the role of libraries in building a new Nigeria.

Challenges Facing Community Libraries in Rural and Urban Areas

There are many problems affecting and hindering proper functioning of libraries in Nigeria, which affects library from contributing effectively to building a new Nigeria.

Low literacy and limited reading culture: The number of people that are literate and able to use library resources are relatively low, especially in rural areas even where libraries are available in urban areas patronage is poor. This situation negates the library function to produce desired developmental objectives. Poor reading culture among the comparatively few literate populations also negatively hinders libraries from producing expected outcome.

Inadequate facilities, staffing and funding: No institution can strive and attain expected goals without adequate resources in terms of human, material and finances. All three elements are grossly inadequate in Nigeria, as such community libraries lack the capacity to achieve result.

Uneven deployment of ICT or digital Access and Power Supply: Many communities in urban and rural areas can stay for months without power supply, as such digital equipment to facilitate online-e-library cannot be utilized. Where power supply is available uneven deployment in terms of availability of network connectivity distort library functioning.

Accessibility, distance and poor infrastructure: Many of our rural communities are inaccessible which affects brining in library service or building to house libraries in rural communities. Distance of people living in remote communities cannot allowed them access library services. As a result of which the social development which prepares them to be good citizens of a new Nigeria cannot reach them.

Overcrowding or high demand with limited resources in urban area is another constraining factor.

Rapid changes in information technology systems, brings the challenge of staying current.

Serving very diverse population with varying needs is also another constraining factor.

More or less near absent of public libraries in rural communities is a grant impediment.

Analyzing Contributions of Community Library Towards Development and Substance of a New Nigeria

Community libraries play a crucial role in national development, particularly in countries striving for transformation like Nigeria. Contributions of community libraries towards the development and sustenance of a new Nigeria, which is one that is informed, inclusive, innovative and democratic can be seen and categorized in several key areas:

Promoting literacy and Education: Community libraries provide access to books and learning materials free or at low cost. This is also true about books and other educational resources. By so doing, community libraries provide support for formal education by providing library space for students to study which boost academic performance. Community library also host adult education and literacy programs, helping to reduce illiteracy rates among the adult population.

Bridging the Digital Divide: It is through community libraries in some communities that basic computer literacy and access to the internet is provided, which help users to gain digital skills needed in today's world. Libraries also help citizens to access online government services and information, which supports transparency and civic engagement.

Empowering youth and women: libraries often organize vocational training, entrepreneurship workshops, and creative skills development in areas of craft, sewing etc. Community libraries provide a safe inclusive environment where women and girls can learn, share and grow without fear of discriminations.

Fostering Civic Engagement and National Identity: Libraries promote knowledge of Nigerian history, the constitution, democratic values, citizens' rights and responsibilities, which are considered as enhancing civic education. Community libraries also serve as venues for town hall meetings, debates and discussions about national issues, fostering community participation in governance. Hence, promoting community dialogue.

Reducing crime and youth restiveness: Community libraries offer productive ways for young people to spend their time, reducing involvement in crime, drug abuse and violence, which provide avenue for constructive engagement. Community libraries help in connecting youth with mentors and role models, thereby contributing to character development and responsible citizenship. In essence, community library is a veritable ground for mentorship opportunities.

Supporting lifelong learning: Community libraries encourage lifelong learning for all age groups through access to diverse knowledge and self-development resources, in which sense, community library is information hubs. The library exposed users to new ideas, technologies and problem solving strategies, thereby contributing to innovation and local solution.

Promoting peace and social inclusion: Community libraries serves as repository of local history, languages, and cultural artifacts, promoting the pride in Nigerian heritage and inter-ethnic understanding, which constitutes cultural preservation. This preservation of culture breed peace, and harmonious co-existence. Libraries serve all segments of society, including people with disabilities, displaced persons, and marginalized communities, which is inclusive service.

Stimulating economic development: libraries provide business guides, market-information, and startup support materials, which help micro, small and medium businesses to grow in which case community libraries are entrepreneurial resources. Libraries often assist with job applicants search for openings, resume writing and vocational guidance, thereby providing job search and career support services.

Ethical reorientation and good governance: Library materials in serials and references are good guides in ethical reorientation and building of public morality. When public morality is achieved good people are available to participate in politics and public decision making which is a way of ensuring accountability, public trust and civic responsibility required in building and sustenance of a new Nigeria.

Prospect and Challenges of Using Community Library as Agent of Social Transformation to a New Nigeria

In analyzing the contributions of community libraries as agent of transformation in Nigeria, it is revealed that community libraries have been playing and will continue to play its pivotal roles in helping to evolve a new Nigeria when problems and pitfalls to its operations and services are corrected or proper attention given. The challenges facing community libraries are numerous and hinder its ability in contributing to socio-economic development and transformation. Community libraries are grossly inadequate in Nigeria. Inadequate funding; lack of consistent government support and limited financial backing from local authorities hinder the operation and growth of community libraries in Nigeria. Many libraries rely on donations and non- governmental organizations, which are often irregular or unsustainable.

Poor Infrastructure: Many libraries operate in dilapidated buildings or temporary structures without basic facilities like electricity, water and toilets. Lack of proper shelving, furniture, lighting and security systems makes the environment uninviting and uncomfortable for users.

Shortage of Qualified Staff: There is significant lack of trained librarians and information professionals. Many libraries are managed by volunteers or untrained individuals, leading to poor service delivery, disorganization and reduced user satisfaction.

Outdated and Insufficient Resources: Many librarians in Nigeria have old, irrelevant or damaged books and learning materials. This cause limited access to current information, digital resources, or educational technology useful for today's information driven world.

Poor ICT Information and Communication Technology Integration: Very few libraries are equipped with computers, internet access or digital learning tools. This instead of closing, widen the digital divide, especially in rural communities, and limit access to modern knowledge.

Low Public Awareness and Patronage: Many communities are unaware of existence or purpose of community libraries. Cultural attitudes and misconceptions that libraries are only for students or elites also discourage use by the broader population, causing exclusion rather than inclusion.

Insecurity and Vandalism: Some libraries, especially in conflict prone or high crime areas are exposed to theft, vandalism or attacks, discouraging use and investment.

Inconsistent Government Policy and Support: There is no robust national policy supporting the development and funding of community libraries. Local governments often do not see libraries as a priority in budgeting or planning.

Consequently, these challenges reduced contribution to library, youth empowerment and civic engagement for socio-economic and political development, inability to support digital skills acquisition, and lifelong learning. The challenges also produce weak impact on community cohesion, peace building and democratic participation, thereby putting a new Nigeria afar.

CONCLUSION

Community libraries are not just about books and enhancement of academic reading culture, they are centers for education empowerment, innovation and social change in building a new Nigeria. The Nigeria desired is a country that is educated, inclusive, democratic and economically vibrant, which rights of citizens are well respected and guaranteed.

Community libraries serve as vital infrastructure, sustained investment for the transformation of institutions and individual to accelerate national development and help ensure lasting peace and prosperity. This is when a new Nigeria will come and the community libraries is a mayor expected contributor.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Major recommendations for community libraries which hold tremendous promises as tools for societal transformation in Nigeria to achieved the desired purpose are;

Establishment of community libraries in all local government areas

Increase funding and policy

Investment in infrastructure, information and communication technology

Community involvement and awareness campaigns

Training and recruitment of qualified personnel with strategic support and reform which will make community libraries to evolve into powerful engines of social development and positive change in Nigeria.

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